

phosphoinositide-specific phospholipase C, $\beta 1$ (PLCB1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : PLCB1 encodes enzyme phospholipase C isoform $\beta 1$ (PLC $\beta 1$), which generates the intracellular second messengers inositol-1,4,5-trisphosphate (Ins-1,4,5- P_3 , also called IP $_3$) and diacylglycerol (DAG) and from phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphonate (PtdIns-4,5- P_2 , also called PIP $_2$). It has been implicated in myocardial infarction, Friend erythroleukemia, schizophrenia, insomnia, malignant migrating partial seizures in infancy, osteogenesis, metastatic breast cancer, Hirschsprung disease, colorectal cancer, glioma, myelodysplastic syndromes and cholangiocarcinoma, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of PLCB1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my

*ML dicoveries of PLCB1 synergy in Meningiomas

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limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: PLCB1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. phosphoinositide-specific phospholipase C, β 1 (PLCB1)

By deletion mapping, Hess et al. [13] determined the extent of the semidominant coloboma (Cm) mutation on mouse Chromosome 2 using interspecific hybrid mice. They found that the Cm deletion mutation resulted in ophthalmic dysmorphology and behavioral deficits, including profound hyperactivity, and was shown to encompass the gene SNAP. In addition to SNAP, the gene encoding phospholipase C β -1 (PLCB1), which mapped 0.60 ± 0.60 cM proximal to SNAP, and simple sequence repeat (SSR) loci D2Mit19, D2Mit46, D2Mit28, and D2Mit136 were shown to be deleted at the Cm

locus. Their data demonstrated that the Cm deletion represented a contiguous gene defect encompassing 1.1 to 2.2 cM that independently affect elements of neurological behavior and eye development.

Maraldi et al. [14] evaluated the intracellular localizations of phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP2) and of its hydrolyzing enzyme PLC β 1 isoform in cells exposed to mitogenic or differentiating agents. Their results demonstrated that in Swiss 3T3 mouse fibroblasts mitogenically stimulated by insulin-like growth factor I (IGF-I), a rapid and transient decrease of the PIP2 happened at the nuclear interior. They propose that this effect appeared due to the activation of the PLC β 1 isoform already present in the nucleus. However, after 30 min of exposure to IGF-I, when the PLC β 1 activity is returned to basal level, an increase of the enzyme was detected both in the nucleus and in the cytoplasm. In contrast, an increased accumulation of PIP2 in the nucleus, accompanied by a decrease of the intranuclear amount of PLC β 1 isoform, was observed in mouse erythroleukemia Friend cells, induced to erythroid differentiation by dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO).

The hydrolysis of inositol lipid by specific PLC constitutes a key step of a signal transduction pathway which further regulates a number of cellular processes. Among PLC isoforms, PLC \sim 1 is of particular interest because of its localization within the nucleus as well as at the plasma membrane. Calabrese et al. [15] reported the chromosome mapping of the rat gene for this PLC isoform and via fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (FISH) analysis, it was assigned the gene coding for PLC \sim t to band q35-36 of rat Chromosome (Chr) 3.

Lyu et al. [16] determined the chromosome positions for 10 mouse PLC genes. They observed that 4 mouse chromosomes, Chr-1/11/12/19, contained single PLC genes. They found that 4 PLC loci, i.e. PLC-B1/B2/B4/G1, mapped to three sites on distal mouse Chr 2. Further, they mapped the human homologs of 8 of these genes to 6 chromosomes by analysis of human x rodent somatic cell hybrids.

Hwang et al. [17] studied the presence of various PLC isoforms in normal human lung tissue from surgical specimens. They partially purified PLC isoforms in tissue extracts of the lung and performed immunohistochemical staining of the lung tissue to determine subcellular and histological localization of PLC isoforms. Their results indicated that normal human lungs contained β -1/3, γ -1, and δ -1, isoforms of PLC. Of these PLC β 1 was localized to the apical membranous portion of the bronchiolar epithelium.

JENCO et al. [18] studied the binding of two G-protein-regulated PLC β -1/2, to membrane surfaces. They observed that PLC β -1/2 bound vesicles composed of phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylethanolamine (molar ratio 1:1:1) with an approximate K_d of 10^{-5} M. Further, PLC β -1/2 contained C2 domains but Ca^{2+} did not enhance binding to the vesicles. Their results pointed to the fact that binding of these enzymes to membranes involved the C-termini of the proteins. It also suggested that activation of these enzymes by G-proteins resulted from a regulated interaction between the membrane-bound proteins rather than G-protein-dependent recruitment of soluble enzymes to a substrate-containing phospholipid surface.

PLC β (4 mammalian isoforms, PLC β -1/2/3/4) catalyses the generation of inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP(3)) and diacylglycerol (DAG) from phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (IP(2)), a key step in the intracellular transduction of a large number

of extracellular signals, including neurotransmitters and hormones modulating diverse developmental and functional aspects of the mammalian central nervous system. Caricasole et al. [19] characterized the human $PLC\beta$ -1 genomic locus, cloned two distinct $PLC\beta$ -1 cDNAs (i.e $PLC\beta$ 1-a/b). Finally, they characterized the structure of the $PLC\beta$ 1 locus and confirmed its mapping to human chromosome 20.

1.3. Roles of $PLC\beta$ 1 in different disease

Large transmural **myocardial infarction** (MI) leads to maladaptive cardiac remodeling and shows increased risk of congestive heart failure. Angiotensin II, endothelin, and alpha1-adrenergic receptor agonists are implicated in the development of cardiac hypertrophy, interstitial fibrosis, and heart failure after MI. Because these agonists are coupled to and activate $G_{q\alpha}$ protein in the heart, Ju et al. [20] explored $G_{q\alpha}$ expression and function in cardiac remodeling and heart failure after MI. For this, they produced MI in rats by ligation of the left coronary artery, and $G_{q\alpha}$ protein concentration, localization, and mRNA abundance were noted in surviving left ventricle remote from the infarct and in border and scar tissues from 8-week post-MI hearts with moderate heart failure. Their Western analysis confirmed upregulation of $G_{q\alpha}$ proteins in border and scar tissues versus controls. Further, increased expression of $PLC\beta$ -1/3 proteins was apparent in the scar and viable tissues after MI versus controls and was associated with increased $PLC\beta$ 1 activity in experimental hearts. Also, inositol 1,4,5-tris-phosphate was significantly increased in the border and scar tissues compared with control values. Thus they concluded that upregulation of the $G_{q\alpha}/PLC\beta$ pathway was observed in the viable, border, and scar tissues in post-MI hearts. They hypothesized that $G_{q\alpha}$ and $PLC\beta$ might play important roles in scar remodeling as well as cardiac hypertrophy and fibrosis of the surviving tissue in post-MI rat heart.

Nuclear phosphoinositide cycle is endowed with kinases as well as phosphatases and phospholipase C (PLC). Among the PLC isozymes, the beta family is characterized by a long COOH-terminal tail that contains a cluster of lysine residues responsible for nuclear localization. $PLC\beta$ 1 is down-regulated during the erythroid differentiation of **Friend erythroleukemia** cells. Matteucci et al. [21] presented evidence that nuclear $PLC\beta$ 1 but not the isoform located at the plasma membrane was directly involved in maintaining the undifferentiated state of Friend erythroleukemia cells. When wild-type $PLC\beta$ 1 was overexpressed in these cells, they observed that differentiation in response to DMSO was inhibited in that the expression of β -globin was almost completely abolished, while when a mutant lacking the ability to localize to the nucleus was expressed, the cells differentiated, and the expression of β -globin was the same as in wild-type cells.

In **schizophrenia** multiple molecular pathways have been reported to be disrupted in the disorder including muscarinic, serotonergic, and glutamatergic signaling systems. $PLC\beta$ 1 acts as a point of convergence for these pathways during cortical development and plasticity and these are susceptible to modulation by RGS4 (a promising candidate gene for schizophrenia). For this, McOmish et al. [22] assessed $PLC\beta$ 1 knockout mice on tests including fear conditioning, elevated plus maze, and the Y maze. They found that $PLC\beta$ 1 knockout mice showed abnormal anxiety profiles on some and decreased anxiety on the elevated plus maze. They further showed memory

impairment and a complete absence of acquisition of hippocampal-dependent fear conditioning. Their results validated the utility of the PLC β 1 knockout mouse as a model of schizophrenia, including molecular and cellular evidence for disrupted cortical maturation and associated behavioral endophenotypes.

Insomnia mostly affects adult population. Ban et al. [23] surveyed 10,038 Korean subjects whose genotypes have been previously profiled on a genome-wide scale and found that insomnia-associated genotypic differences were highly concentrated within genes involved in neural function. They observed that the most significant SNPs resided in ROR1 and PLCB1 (known to be involved in bipolar disorder and schizophrenia, respectively). They discovered enhancers, as indicated by the histone mark H3K4me1, within both genes near the significant SNPs and in neuronal cells, the enhancers were bound by PAX6 (a neural transcription factor that is important for central nervous system development). Further, in PLCB1, CTCF was found to bind downstream of the enhancer and interact with PAX6, suggesting that it could probably inhibit gene activation by PAX6. Thus they hypothesized that dysregulation of ROR1, PLCB-1/4 by PAX6 and CTCF might be one mechanism that linked neural and pancreatic dysfunction not only in insomnia but also in the relevant psychiatric disorders. These disorders are accompanied with circadian rhythm disruption and metabolic syndrome.

Malignant migrating partial seizures in infancy (MMPEI) is an early onset epileptic encephalopathy with few known etiologies. Poduri et al. [24] sought to identify a novel cause of MMPEI in a child with MMPEI whose healthy parents were consanguineous and found that the proband had an inherited homozygous deletion of chromosome 20p13, disrupting the promoter region and first 3 coding exons of the gene PLCB1. Their results pointed that loss of PLCB1 function was one cause of MMPEI, which was in-line with prior studies in a PLCB1 knockout mouse model that developed early onset severe childhood epilepsy.

Bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP-2) is a critical growth factor that directs osteoblast differentiation and bone formation, while PLC β 1 plays a crucial role in the initiation of the genetic program responsible for muscle differentiation. Further, differentiation of C2C12 mouse myoblasts in response to insulin stimulation was characterized by a marked increase in nuclear PLC β 1. Ramazzotti et al. [25] explored the function of PLC β 1 in the osteogenic differentiation. Their data regarding the influence on differentiation demonstrated that PLC β 1 promotes osteogenic differentiation by up-regulating alkaline phosphatase (ALP). miR-214 being a regulator of Osterix (Osx) (an osteoblast-specific transcription factor needed for osteoblast differentiation and bone formation), they investigated whether PLC β 1 could be a potential target of miR-214 in the control of osteogenic differentiation by gain/loss- of function experiment. Their results indicated that inhibition of miR-214 in C2C12 cells significantly enhanced the protein level of PLC β 1 and promoted C2C12 BMP-2-induced **osteogenesis** by targeting PLC β 1.

Altered abundance of phosphatidyl inositides (PIs) is a feature of cancer. Sengelaub et al. [26] found that PTPRN2 and PLC β 1 reduced plasma membrane phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate PI(4,5)P2 levels in **metastatic breast cancer** cells through two independent mechanisms. These genes were upregulated in highly metastatic breast cancer cells, and their increased expression associates with human metastatic

relapse. Their findings revealed an enzymatic network that regulated metastatic cell migration through lipid-dependent sequestration of an actin-remodeling factor.

Circular RNA_PRKCI (circ-PRKCI) has been reported to regulate cell proliferation, migration and invasion in several human cancers. **Hirschsprung disease** (HSCR) is a well-known congenital gut motility disorder which roots in the aberrance of cranial-caudal neural crest cell migration. Zhou et al. [27] explored whether circ-PRKCI might affect cell migration and proliferation in HSCR. They found that circ-PRKCI was down-regulated in HSCR aganglionic tissues and mechanistically confirmed that circ-PRKCI functioned as a molecular sponge for miR-1324 to upregulate the expression of PLCB1. Thus they concluded the important role of circ-PRKCI-miR-1324-PLCB1 regulatory network in HSCR.

Lu et al. [28] investigated the effects of microRNA-124 (miR-124) on tumor proliferation of **colorectal cancer** (CRC) in vivo and in vitro. They concluded that miR-124 inhibited tumor cell proliferation in vitro and suppressed tumor growth in vivo by interacting with PLCB1 and regulating the Wnt/-catenin signaling pathway.

Zhao et al. [29] tried to confirm that PLCB1 played a critical role in suppressing **glioma** progression. Taken together, they deduced that miR-423-5p inhibited proliferation and metastasis by targeting PLCB1, and it also promoted apoptosis in glioma cells. Their results suggested that miR-423-5p directly targeted PLCB1 3'-UTR and could inhibit cell invasion and migration through the ERK-dependent pathway in glioma. Thus, the miR-423-5p/PLCB1 axis might be a potential target for new potential therapeutic strategies to treat glioma.

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS) are characterized by anemia and transfusion requirements. Transfused patients are known show iron overload that negatively affects hematopoiesis. To this effect, Cappellini et al. [30] studied the molecular features of iron effect and Deferasirox therapy on PI-PLC β 1 inositide signaling, using hematopoietic cells and MDS samples. At baseline, they observed that MDS patients showed a positive response after iron chelation therapy displayed higher levels of PI-PLC β 1/Cyclin D3/PKC α expression. Further, during treatment, these responder patients, as well as hematopoietic cells treated with FeCl₃ and Deferasirox, showed a specific reduction of PI-PLC β 1/Cyclin D3/PKC α expression, indicating that this signaling pathway was targeted by Deferasirox. Thus, their data showed that PI-PLC β 1 signaling was a target for iron-induced oxidative stress and suggested that baseline PI-PLC β 1 quantification could predict iron chelation therapy response in MDS.

Liang et al. [31] uncovered a role for PLCB1 in **cholangiocarcinoma** (CCA) progression and identified the underlying mechanisms. They found that both human CCA tissues and CCA cell lines expressed high levels of PLCB1 and their data identified a PLCB1-PI3K-AKT signaling axis vital for CCA development and EMT, while suggesting that AKT could be used as a therapeutic target to overcome chemotherapy resistance in CCA patients with high PLCB1 expression.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [32] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [33] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [33].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on

gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [34]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [35], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [32] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tunned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [32]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [36], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings

provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PLCB1 related synergies

Note - PLCB1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of PLCB1 were recorded.

3.1.1. PLCB1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PLCB1 showed high rankings - heat shock protein family B (small) member 6 (HSPB6), calcium voltage-gated channel subunit alpha 1 G (CACNA1G), prominin 1 (PROM1), flavin containing dimethylaniline monooxygenase 1 (FMO1), insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF1), elastin (ELN), neuron navigator 3 (NAV3), LIM and cysteine rich domains 1 (LMCD1), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), fibulin 1 (FBLN1), ADCYAP receptor type I (ADCYAP1R1), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), transmembrane protein 59 like (TMEM59L), secreted frizzled related protein 4 (SFRP4), AE binding protein 1 (AEBP1), Kazal type serine peptidase inhibitor domain 1 (KAZALD1), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), bone marrow stromal cell antigen 1 (BST1), neurexin 2 (NRXN2), GLI family zinc finger 1 (GLI1), ST8 alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminide alpha-2,8-sialyltransferase 1 (ST8SIA1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), lysyl oxidase like 3 (LOXL3), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), hippocalcin like 4 (HPCAL4), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 2 (LTBP2), collagen type X alpha 1 chain (COL10A1), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), matrilin 4 (MATN4), neuritin 1 (NRN1), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), matrilin 3 (MATN3), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), peripherin (PRPH), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), integrin subunit alpha 11 (ITGA11), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), NKD inhibitor of WNT signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), secreted frizzled related protein 2 (SFRP2), family with sequence similarity 105 member A (FAM105A), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRNB3), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), ABI family member 3

binding protein (ABI3BP), chromosome 10 open reading frame 90 (C10orf90), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM1), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), PDZ domain containing ring finger 4 (PDZRN4), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), serine/threonine kinase 32A (STK32A), secretogranin II (SCG2), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (AKAP19 / C2orf88), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 3124 (LINC03124 / C2orf27A), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase 29 (DUSP29 / DUSP27), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PLCB1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t PLCB1 with PLCB1 – > HSPB6 / CACNA1G / PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 / ELN / NAV3 / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 / ADCYAP1R1

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PLCB1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PLCB1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
HSPB6 - PLCB1	291	199	258	383	CACNA1G - PLCB1	324	346	274	387
PROM1 - PLCB1	298	330	219	343	FMO1 - PLCB1	182	285	300	386
IGF1 - PLCB1	288	270	154	317	ELN - PLCB1	252	335	227	91
NAV3 - PLCB1	203	316	277	381	LMCD1 - PLCB1	318	321	218	348
SLC12A1 - PLCB1	322	368	313	369	FBLN1 - PLCB1	355	363	260	318
ADCYAP1R1 - PLCB1	270	249	328	169	SRPX - PLCB1	293	325	208	379
PCSK1N - PLCB1	225	313	217	130	SLC17A7 - PLCB1	307	289	231	108
TMEM59L - PLCB1	213	230	238	177	SFRP4 - PLCB1	309	365	293	364
AEBP1 - PLCB1	224	258	319	45	KAZALD1 - PLCB1	299	302	214	15
EBF1 - PLCB1	273	293	263	12	BST1 - PLCB1	296	384	205	389
NRXN2 - PLCB1	209	328	271	141	GLI1 - PLCB1	274	362	239	250
ST8SIA1 - PLCB1	366	377	298	345	NPR3 - PLCB1	297	356	257	283
SLC30A3 - PLCB1	287	306	356	373	LOXL3 - PLCB1	351	132	244	265
PRG4 - PLCB1	277	248	288	125	HPCAL4 - PLCB1	284	303	248	204
TRIM67 - PLCB1	311	345	340	258	LTBP2 - PLCB1	286	257	268	100
COL10A1 - PLCB1	231	206	253	101	PLP1 - PLCB1	337	274	192	337
MATN4 - PLCB1	330	187	207	388	NRN1 - PLCB1	247	200	250	32
RUNX2 - PLCB1	240	391	206	10	LAMP5 - PLCB1	378	338	341	368
KIF1A - PLCB1	338	350	308	326	PODNL1 - PLCB1	354	169	302	338
MATN3 - PLCB1	234	286	245	384	SERPINF1 - PLCB1	254	284	318	327
PTPN22 - PLCB1	53	231	224	242	PRPH - PLCB1	258	353	317	346
FAIM2 - PLCB1	242	266	267	67	SCN7A - PLCB1	333	375	334	256
TTC29 - PLCB1	272	389	247	334	THBS1 - PLCB1	313	280	315	355
ITGA11 - PLCB1	257	380	189	380	DUOX1 - PLCB1	262	134	200	332
LHCGR - PLCB1	280	327	323	370	RBP4 - PLCB1	335	311	335	339
DUOX2 - PLCB1	271	140	241	385	FGF7 - PLCB1	385	359	301	354
NKD1 - PLCB1	265	373	305	362	RCN3 - PLCB1	241	360	198	74
NXPH2 - PLCB1	347	390	338	344	SFRP2 - PLCB1	261	319	221	55
FAM105A - PLCB1	154	235	212	286	CHRN3 - PLCB1	336	357	303	350
NTRK2 - PLCB1	269	374	230	281	DRD2 - PLCB1	323	339	279	376
KCNA6 - PLCB1	345	354	306	335	ABI3BP - PLCB1	285	305	265	340
C10orf90 - PLCB1	197	238	177	382	PDE1C - PLCB1	340	309	309	329
PPP2R2B - PLCB1	251	278	242	320	S100B - PLCB1	290	318	330	375

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLCB1 VS Individual members.

/ SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / TMEM59L / SFRP4 / AEBP1 / KAZALD1 / EBF1 / BST1 / NRXN2 / GLI1 / ST8SIA1 / NPR3 / SLC30A3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / HPCAL4 / TRIM67 / LTBP2 / COL10A1 / PLP1 / MATN4 / NRN1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / MATN3 / SERPINF1 / PTPN22 / PRPH / FAIM2 / SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / SFRP2 / FAM105A / CHRN3 / NTRK2 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / PDE1C / PPP2R2B / S100B / COL26A1 / VCAM1 / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / DACT2 / CA3 / PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / NNMT / ENHO / STK32A / SCG2 / SERTM1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / ENTPD8 / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PLCB1											
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PLCB1											
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		
COL26A1 - PLCB1	306	323	354	356	VCAM1 - PLCB1	117	287	203	392		
FRZB - PLCB1	245	237	216	378	C1QTNF7 - PLCB1	319	343	296	349		
RHOBTB3 - PLCB1	308	314	304	323	EBF1 - PLCB1	273	293	263	12		
DACT2 - PLCB1	295	290	252	28	CA3 - PLCB1	260	383	310	156		
PDZRN4 - PLCB1	339	381	280	291	TMEM130 - PLCB1	304	355	322	357		
NNMT - PLCB1	259	388	324	328	ENHO - PLCB1	226	382	226	33		
STK32A - PLCB1	289	387	240	231	SCG2 - PLCB1	325	385	347	367		
SERTM1 - PLCB1	365	341	272	365	NTM - PLCB1	156	217	314	371		
RGS6 - PLCB1	283	2	295	324	PAPP - PLCB1	275	192	321	347		
PYCR1 - PLCB1	380	351	374	290	NEB - PLCB1	374	276	355	161		
TMEM119 - PLCB1	326	202	327	51	OLFML1 - PLCB1	301	215	373	57		
DUSP5P1 - PLCB1	348	364	344	60	ADRA2C - PLCB1	361	281	350	99		
CSF1 - PLCB1	377	372	377	216	FLRT2 - PLCB1	367	291	333	83		
PRKG1 - PLCB1	372	261	369	202	SHC4 - PLCB1	292	225	339	54		
CYP4Z1 - PLCB1	379	226	357	199	CYP4X1 - PLCB1	362	366	385	244		
RTN4RL2 - PLCB1	381	344	389	271	C2orf88 - PLCB1	391	367	361	195		
KBTBD12 - PLCB1	389	333	353	118	ENTPD8 - PLCB1	353	239	345	129		
FAM180A - PLCB1	199	7	292	363	STK31 - PLCB1	383	334	326	238		
MME - PLCB1	227	150	275	366	DACT3 - PLCB1	371	315	352	331		
ADARB1 - PLCB1	357	322	382	160	SPN - PLCB1	388	340	359	222		
C2orf27A - PLCB1	368	220	380	321	CLEC9A - PLCB1	302	269	337	44		
DLGAP2 - PLCB1	300	204	312	48	MT1F - PLCB1	385	210	363	139		
ITGBL1 - PLCB1	370	369	364	207	DLL1 - PLCB1	376	279	346	63		
ZNF521 - PLCB1	278	229	348	299	RYR3 - PLCB1	341	178	336	390		
DUSP27 - PLCB1	390	392	390	305	RNU6-529P - PLCB1	382	263	381	167		
RHOTIP2 - PLCB1	342	129	297	353	PLPP4 - PLCB1	310	242	329	302		
TMEM240 - PLCB1	320	348	343	89	ANKRD20A9P - PLCB1	106	243	213	361		
HACD2 - PLCB1	387	138	378	257	HMGB3P7 - PLCB1	220	310	367	13		
ANKRD20A11P - PLCB1	294	94	311	374	TENM3 - PLCB1	172	264	204	358		
RFP1S - PLCB1	369	376	384	219	LINC00937 - PLCB1	392	347	391	285		
LINC01907 - PLCB1	364	317	386	254	ITGB2-AS1 - PLCB1	303	240	331	47		
CYP4F29P - PLCB1	264	114	316	352	ZNF883 - PLCB1	346	370	383	261		
SNX18P13 - PLCB1	244	72	281	336							

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PLCB1 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PLCB1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PLCB1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PLCB1

HSPB6 / CACNA1G / PROM1 / FMO1 / IGF1 ...
ELN / NAV3 / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / FBLN1 ...
ADCYAP1R1 / SRPX / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 ...
TMEM59L / SFRP4 / AEBP1 / KAZALD1 ...
EBF1 / BST1 / NRXN2 / GLI1 / ST8SIA1 ...
NPR3 / SLC30A3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / HPCAL4 ...
TRIM67 / LTBP2 / COL10A1 / PLP1 / MATN4 ...
NRN1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / KIF1A / PODNL1 ...
MATN3 / SERPINF1 / PTPN22 / PRPH / FAIM2 ...
SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / ITGA11 / DUOX1 ...
LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOX2 / FGF7 / NKD1 / RCN3 ...
NXPH2 / SFRP2 / FAM105A / CHRNB3 / NTRK2 ...
DRD2 / KCNA6 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / PDE1C ...
PPP2R2B / S100B / COL26A1 / VCAM1 / FRZB ...
C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 / EBF1 / DACT2 / CA3 ...
PDZRN4 / TMEM130 / NNMT / ENHO / STK32A ...
SCG2 / SERTM1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 ...
NEB / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C ...
CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 ...
CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 ...
ENTPD8 / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / DACT3 ...
ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 ...
MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 ...
DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 ...
TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / HMGB3P7 ...
ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 ...
LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13 PLCB1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PLCB1 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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